

Charles V's letter to the Cologne estates (1546/47). A call for "Revolution" against Archbishop Hermann von Wied?

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Abstract

In the 1540s, Archbishop Hermann von Wied attempted to introduce some form of Reformation or at least church reform in his territory, the Archbishopric Cologne. This attempt at reformation was extraordinary in two aspects. Firstly, it was not clearly oriented along the principles of the Protestant or Reformed reformation in the way of Luther, Calvin or Zwingli, but it was rather an attempt to hold a middle position between the orthodox Catholic side and the Protestant one theologically as well as politically. Secondly, it failed and ended in the deposition of Hermann von Wied as archbishop. This is remarkable since it is not only removed of a church authority from its position but also of a prince and sovereign of a territory. This deposition in a legal sense followed the announcement of the imperial ban¹ and excommunication of Hermann von Wied, and in the end, was carried out after the decision of a Landtag (local diet). This Diet came together after a letter of Emperor Charles V to Cologne's estates in which he ordered them to meet. This paper analyses this letter as well as a pamphlet proclaiming the excommunication in German. It will show if the deposition by the estates

¹ The imperial ban, in German *Reichsacht*, was a legal act inside the Holy Roman Empire declaring a person outlawed throughout the empire.

happened from below by the estates and how they were influenced by the emperor and the pope as from the authorities on the level above their immediate liege, the archbishop.

Introduction

Historical scholarship has repeatedly dealt with Hermann von Wied and his failed attempt to introduce Reformation in the Archbishopric of Cologne. As early as the eighteenth and early nineteenth century, a debate took place in the context of the history of the Reformation. At the end of the nineteenth century, Georg Drouven produced a publication of the sources and Conrad Varrentrapp compiled a detailed biography. After the Second World War and the 400th anniversary, a number of shorter writings on the subject appeared, such as by Hubert Jedin and Lutz Hatzfeld, who focused on the Wetterau counts. More recently, Badea, with her examination from the perspective of the "Electoral Preeminence;" Stephan Laux, who worked on the Reformation in the estates; and Theodor Schlüter, with his edition of the publications in the context of the Reformation attempt, are worthy of mention. On the other hand, this work focuses on the act of deposition itself as well as the imperial call for it. The paper proposes the following research questions: How is the deposition of an early modern prince, especially a prince of the church, justified? By whom was this ultimately carried out? How far a political upheaval, such as the deposition of Hermann von Wied, can be interpreted as a revolution?

Definitions of "revolution" for the early modern period

What constitutes a revolution is disputed in historiography. Common definitions are mostly based on phenomena from the French Revolution onwards. In the *Enzyklopädie der Neuzeit*, for example, Reichert differentiates between the “early modern revolution” of the old type and the “modern revolution,” among which the focus is on the French Revolution. For him, early modern revolutions are characterised by biblical fundamentalism and a movement that emerges from the people, in contrast to later ones.² Niggemann finds a minimal definitional consensus for revolutions: “Processes in the course of which comprehensive changes with regard to the political and social structures of a society as well as the exchange of political elites are achieved in a relatively short time by violent means.”³ For him, it is important to move away from the template of the French Revolution and to take earlier events into account as well.⁴ Pincus, on the other hand, follows Reichardt’ and Niggemann’s definitions insofar as he describes revolutions as a structural and ideological break with the previous regime, which leads to upheavals of political and socio-economic structures. This can be linked to a violent movement from below. What is also decisive for him is the question of when revolutions occur. He does not see them as a conflict between the conservative and a modernisation movement, but rather as a directional decision in an already ongoing transformation process.⁵

² Reichardt, Rolf, “Revolution”, in: *Enzyklopädie der Neuzeit Online*. Consulted online on 14 December 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2352-0248_edn_COM_339983>. First published online: 2019.

³ “Vorgänge, im Zuge derer mit gewaltsamen Mitteln relativ kurzfristig umfassende Veränderungen im Hinblick auf die politischen und sozialen Strukturen einer Gesellschaft sowie der Austausch der politischen Eliten erreicht werden” Ulrich Niggemann, *Revolutionserinnerung in der Frühen Neuzeit: Refiguration der “Glorius Revolution” in Großbritannien (1688-1760)* (Boston: De Gruyter Oldenbourg, 2017.), 5.

⁴ Niggemann, *Revolutionserinnerung*, 12.

⁵ Steve Pincus, *1688: The first modern Revolution* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2009), 33.

The Archbishopric of Cologne under Hermann von Wied

Hermann von Wied was born in Wied in 1477 into the local dynasty of counts. The Counts of Wied were members of the Wetterauer Grafenverein (Wetterau Counts' Association),⁶ which represented an important power bloc in the environment of the Archbishopric of Cologne, especially as its members were *stiftsfähig*⁷ in Cologne. In 1490, at the age of 13, Hermann von Wied became a canon in Cologne, and in 1503, he was appointed as head of the chancery of the archbishopric by the cathedral chapter. On 13 April 1515, he was elected as Archbishop of Cologne, succeeding Philipp von Daum. This made him not only an ecclesiastical authority but also a secular sovereign who, as Elector, stood at the highest level, below the Emperor, in the hierarchy of the Holy Roman Empire of the German Nation. Notable events from the first years of his reign include his consecration as bishop, which did not take place until 1518, the royal coronation of Charles V, which he performed in Aachen in 1520, and his conflict with the city of Cologne, which did not allow him to ceremonially enter Cologne until 1522.⁸ The city of Cologne had been politically independent from the archbishops since the thirteenth century, but it continued to be the regional centre of the Rhineland and was significant for the archbishops who moved to Bonn.

In the 1520s, Hermann von Wied found himself on the Catholic-imperial side in the conflicts over the Reformation. In 1521, he supported the ban of Martin Luther (1483-1546) and was among the signatories of the Edict of Worms.⁹ As a result, Luther's writings were outlawed in Hermann von Wied's territories and the persecution of Protestants as heretics began in the

⁶ Stephan Laux, *Reformationsversuche in Kurköln (1542-1548): Fallstudien zu einer Strukturgeschichte landständischer Reformation (Neuss, Kempen, Andernach, Linz)* (Münster: Aschendorff, 200), 67-68.

⁷ *Stiftsfähigkeit* describes the eligibility of a certain group for the post of canon at a cathedral.

⁸ Stupperich, Robert, "Hermann V." in: *Neue Deutsche Biographie* 8 (1969), S. 636-637 [Online-Version]; URL: <https://www.deutsche-biographie.de/pnd118702793.html#ndbcontent>.

⁹ Andreea Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz, Landesherrschaft und Reform: Das Scheitern der Kölner Reformation unter Hermann von Wied* (Münster: Aschendorff, 2009), 185. The Edict of Worms proclaimed the imperial ban over Martin Luther and with that made him an outlaw in the empire.

course of the 1520s. This was carried out in the Duchy of Westphalia as well, since Hermann von Wied's appointment as administrator of the Bishopric of Paderborn in 1530 it was an integral part of the territories controlled by the Archbishops of Cologne again. According to Jedin, this action against Lutherans is to be seen more like the action of an imperial prince than that of a bishop.¹⁰ For Hermann von Wied, Lutheranism was not a theological problem but a political one. His actions were not driven by the dissenting beliefs per se but by the resulting unrest and threat to the *Landfrieden*.¹¹

As a solution to the question of the Reformation, Hermann von Wied strove for a conciliar solution for the empire, which could have led to a special path within the Catholic Church for the territories of the Holy Roman Empire which, however, never came about. He stuck to this plan until his deposition. Latest by the 1530s, Hermann von Wied assumed a special role in his external perception. In 1530, Hermann von Wied was described by Emperor Charles V as “neither Catholic nor Lutheran, rather a pagan”.¹² Although von Wied was perceived by others as distancing himself from Lutheranism and the Protestant princes of the Holy Roman Empire, this deviation from Catholic orthodoxy posed a problem for the Emperor in terms of imperial policy. In the course of the decade, criticism about von Wied came from all sides, the papal nuncio and Luther himself.¹³ As late as 1540, other Rhenish princes, namely Trier, Jülich and the Electoral Palatinate, were still perceived as “impartial” in the conflict between the emperor and the Protestants.¹⁴ The 1530s were also marked by the beginning of Hermann von Wied's reform programme in the Archbishopric of Cologne. On the one hand, comprehensive

¹⁰ Hubert Jedin, “Fragen um Hermann von Wied,” *Historisches Jahrbuch* 74 (1954): 692.

¹¹ *Landfrieden* describes the concept of internal peace in a territory in the late medieval and early modern period. This peace was to be achieved by jurisdictional measurements and should stop feuds and revolts.

¹² “Weder katholisch noch lutherisch, eher ein Heide” Jedin, *Fragen um Hermann von Wied*, 692.

¹³ Jedin, “Fragen um Hermann von Wied,” 692.

¹⁴ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Päminenz*, 5.

administrative reforms took place,¹⁵ which concerned the judicial system,¹⁶ the police code,¹⁷ a mining code, and the coinage system as well. These reforms aimed to get the administration of the territory up to the standards of the time but, above all, to preserve the Landfrieden. On the other hand, a first attempt at reforming the church order was carried out in 1536. This came about through a provincial synod in the archdiocese. The Enchiridion of Johann Gropper was the authoritative document of this first church reform under Hermann von Wied.¹⁸ This reform was supported by the Erasmian circles surrounding the archbishop, the neighbouring territories of Jülich-Kleve-Berg and the imperial city of Cologne.¹⁹ However, a complete church reform in the Erasmian sense did not take place in Cologne, in contrast to the neighbouring Jülich-Kleve-Berg.²⁰ Humanism as a drive for church reform on the archbishop's side, remains questionable, since Hermann, according to Jedin, was not a humanist in the sense of Erasmus, not even an “intellectual” by contemporary standards.²¹

¹⁵ Wolf-Dietrich Penning, *Die weltlichen Zentralbehörden im Erzstift Köln: Von der ersten Hälfte des 15. bis zum Beginn des 17. Jahrhunderts* (Bonn: Ludwig Röhrscheid-Verlag, 1977), 60-61.

¹⁶ Elisabeth M. Kloosterhuis, *Erasmusjünger als politische Reformer: Humanismusideal und Herrschaftspraxis am Niederrhein im 16 Jahrhundert* (Köln: Böhlau, 2006), 37-45.

¹⁷ Kloosterhuis, *Erasmusjünger*, 34-37.

¹⁸ Kloosterhuis, *Erasmusjünger*, 59.

¹⁹ Kloosterhuis, *Erasmusjünger*, 54-59.

²⁰ The church reforms that are called erasmian oriented are rooted in the humanistic movement and oriented themselves along the teachings of Erasmus of Rotterdam (1466-1536) and other humanists influenced by him. Via new church order and clerical and public education they tried to find a way to remedy the insufficiencies that led to the Reformation without taking a reformatory or orthodox Catholic standpoint.

²¹ Jedin, *Fragen um Hermann von Wied*, 691-692.

The Cologne Reformation

Instead of continuing these reforms, Hermann von Wied turned away from the Catholic orthodoxy from 1540 onwards and moved closer to Protestantism. This happened under the impressions of his participation as a moderate Catholic representative at the religious discussions of Hagenau, Worms and Regensburg in 1540 and 1541.²² On these occasions, he also got to know Martin Butzer(1491-1551), who took part in them on the Protestant side. Butzer had already turned to Protestantism in the early 1520s and was active as a reformer in the following years in the regions of modern-day south Germany and eastern France, especially in Strasbourg. As a reaction to the Regensburg Interim of 1541, in which a provisional church reform within the dioceses by the imperial prelates was demanded, Hermann initiated a new church reform - even though the validity of this part of the Regensburg Interim for the territory of Electorate Cologne was questionable.²³ Johann Gropper(1503-1559), who aimed to continue the internal Catholic reform, was entrusted with the task to formulate a new church order. Gropper, being a cleric that rose through the ranks in the Archbishopric of Cologne, had already been entrusted with the earlier administrative reforms of the territory. In 1542, Martin Butzer was also called to Cologne by Hermann von Wied. After initial cooperation between Gropper and Butzer, a break occurred in 1543 with the beginning of Butzer's sermons in Bonn. In these sermons, it became clear that Butzer and his patron, the archbishop, did not have a purely internal Catholic reform in mind but that reformatory ideas were to be implemented. This led to a letter of protest from the majority of the cathedral chapter. This resistance was mainly carried out by the university, priest canons and the secondary clergy of the Archbishopric of Cologne. In the following years, the university embodied the resistance to the Reformation by

²² Laux, *Reformationsversuche in Kurköln*, 70-71.

²³ Badaea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 18.

educated bourgeois circles in the city of Cologne.²⁴ In reaction to Butzer's sermons, Johann Gropper ventured a final proposal for Catholic reform. This was taken up by Hermann von Wied, who tried to pacify Catholic and Protestant groups in the archbishopric by involving both Butzer and Gropper. Through this and the assertion that the new church order was an implementation of the recess of the imperial Diet of Regensburg, Hermann von Wied succeeded in gaining approval for his reform plans at the Märzlandtag, a diet of the estates of Cologne in March 1543. Butzer was now exclusively entrusted with the implementation, Gropper from now on formed an opposition from the city of Cologne with the majority chapter that remained Catholic.²⁵ After the approval of the Estates, Butzer sought Protestant support for the project. After Johann Pistorius the Elder(1504-1583), a reformer in Hesse, could not be won over, Philipp Melanchthon(1497-1560) was brought in.²⁶ Butzer and Melanchthon drew up the *Einfältige Bedenken*, which was the central document of the Cologne Reformation attempt. It was completed in July 1543, and after its acceptance by the Estates, was printed in September of the same year. In terms of content, this new church order combined traditional church institutions, such as monasteries and convents, with reformatory ideas in the doctrine of justification and the sacraments. A special emphasis was placed on improving pastoral care.²⁷ In addition to rejection by the *Altgläubigen* (those who remained catholic) and by the protest faction of the cathedral chapter, it also received criticism from Protestants, and even from Luther himself. The dissent originated in the Marburg Colloquy of 1529, and the differing views on the issue of the sacraments. The *Einfältige Bedenken* was influenced by various church constitutions of Protestant territories in the empire that had already been written in the 1530s.

²⁴ Lutz Hatzfeld, "Dr. Gropper, die Wetterauer Grafen und die Reformation in Kurköln 1537/1547," *Archiv für Kulturgeschichte* 36 (1954): 225, <https://doi.org/10.7788/akg-1954-jg11>.

²⁵ A list of all the members of the cathedral chapter of Cologne and their positioning can be found with Hatzfeld, "Die Wetterauer Grafen", 228-229.

²⁶ Jedin, "Fragen um Hermann von Wied," 696.

²⁷ Laux, *Reformationsversuche in Kurköln*, 72-73.

Hermann von Wied himself intervened in the creation of the *Bedenkens* in favour of the landständische nobility (landed nobility) so that he would not lose their support.²⁸ In terms of foreign policy, this phase of the Cologne Reformation is marked by the Geldrian War of Succession between Emperor Charles V and Wilhem of Kleve-Jülich-Berg. The primary issues were the inheritance of the Duchy of Guelders and influence in the Netherlands and on the Rhine, which was of decisive importance for the Archbishopric of Cologne due to the geographical proximity and the episcopal responsibility for the territory.²⁹ However, Catholic orthodoxy represented by the Emperor was opposed by a more reform-oriented prince, William of Cleves(1539-1592). Although the church reform in Jülich-Kleve-Berg was Erasmian, the support of this regional power was necessary for the implementation of Hermann von Wied's plans. The defeat of William of Cleves at Düren was the first major setback for the Reformation on the Rhine. Nonetheless, Hubert Jedin does not see this as the end of the Reformation, as various twists and turns were taken before his deposition.³⁰

In 1544, the Catholic majority of the cathedral chapter appealed to the pope and emperor, asking them to intervene for the Catholic cause.³¹ They were not supported by the cathedral chapters of the other Rhenish electors³², but by the bishops of Liège and Utrecht who were subordinate to the Archbishop of Cologne in religious matters.³³ The conflict between the cathedral chapter and the archbishop was going on in court trials before the emperor and the pope. While a break with Rome became increasingly clear, Hermann tried to prevent condemnation by the emperor. The controversial question was whether the *Einfältiges Bedenken* and the innovations in the

²⁸ Jedin, "Fragen um Hermann von Wied," 696-697.

²⁹ Kloosterhuis, *Erasmusjünger*, 73-74.

³⁰ Jedin, "Fragen um Hermann von Wied," 697.

³¹ Badaea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 78-86.

³² Jedin, "Fragen um Hermann von Wied," 697-698.

³³ Paul III., *Das Päpstlich vrteil*, fol. Av.

church constitution, as general questions of faith, could be decided on without a resolution of a new provincial council.³⁴ Just like the War of the Geldrian Succession had an influence as a foreign policy framework at the beginning of the Cologne Reformation, this was all the more the case with the conflict between the Schmalkaldic League and the emperor. This alliance of Protestant princes had tried to win Hermann over to their side and supported him against the emperor. However, the Electorate of Cologne never joined the Schmalkaldic League, as Hermann continued to try to play both sides and was never fully prepared to break with the Emperor. The differing interests of Saxony and Hesse, the two leading powers of the League, made concrete support difficult.³⁵ Nevertheless, in the archbishop's environment, the counts of Wetterau had little interest in a possible strengthening of Hesse.³⁶

The intervention of the authorities

The trial in front of the emperor came to an end on 26 January 1546 with the imposition of the imperial ban on Hermann von Wied, before the Schmalkaldic League had been able to provide any considerable support.³⁷ This, however, did not mean the end of Hermann's rule. The cathedral chapter and the estates did not want to enforce the ban without a papal judgement. In the spring of 1546, the papacy finally intervened in the conflict. On 16 April 1546, Pope Paul III(1534-1549) excommunicated Hermann von Wied, but this was not publicly announced until 16 August 1546.³⁸ The pope did not intervene of his own accord, but acted on an appeal by the

³⁴ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 82-83.

³⁵ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 111-120.

³⁶ Hatzfeld, *Die Wetterauer Grafen*, 214.

³⁷ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 183-186; Dorothee Mußnug, *Acht und Bann im 15. und 16. Jahrhundert* (Berlin: Duncker & Humblot, 2016), 264. Mußnug sees in the *Declaratoria Sententia* a mere renouncement of the degrees, in which an imperial ban was only threatened by acting against. This stands in contrast to the bans against the heads of the Schmalkaldic League.

³⁸ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 199-200.

Catholic party at the Curia. The plaintiffs here were not only the Catholic majority chapter which had turned away from Hermann but also the University of Cologne and the bishops of the Bishoprics of Liège and Utrecht, both subordinate to Cologne. These parties, too, would ultimately have been affected by such a church reform on the ecclesiastical level.

Although the Latin excommunication was also distributed in printed form³⁹, the decision probably became known by the wider public rather through the German-language writing of Johann Baptista Cicada (1543-1554), the bishop of Albenga.⁴⁰ In this text, printed in Augsburg, he summarises the papal sentences. Particularly impressive is the frontispiece of the pamphlet, which consists of two text pyramids with a German translation of the excommunication. In the upper one, the pope at the behest of the “dignified Clergy”, the majority of the cathedral chapter and the “high school,”⁴¹ that is to say the University of Cologne, recognised that Hermann had become unfit as Archbishop of Cologne and administrator of the Bishopric of Paderborn since he had been deprived of all honour and dignity in the archbishopric and bishopric due to “many improper reforms in the question of religion”.⁴² There is a clear reference to the appellants and the reason for the excommunication - the new church order. His unfitness for the office of archbishop derived from his actions. The second pyramid proclaimed that the Pope had absolved all the ecclesiastical and secular estates committed to Hermann von Wied of all oaths and duties to him.⁴³ This way, von Wied was practically deposed politically as well, and continuing to hold power would have been conceivable only as a Protestant sovereign detached from the Church. What is astonishing is that Cicada added the appellation as the second part of

³⁹ Theodor C. Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften zur “Kölner Reformation”*: Die Publizistik um den Reformationsversuch des Kölner Erzbischofs und Kurfürsten Hermann von Wied (1515-1547) (Wiesbaden: Hassarowitz Verlag, 2005), 307-308.

⁴⁰ Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 309.

⁴¹ “Erwürdigen Clereseey”; “hohen Schul”; Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 309.

⁴² “viler unzimlicher newerung in der religion” Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 309.

⁴³ Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 309.

the text after publishing the papal judgment - as announced in the second pyramid. The appeal practically became the justification for the judgment. The final section of the leaflet made it clear how serious the Catholic Church was about banning the Archbishop of Cologne. An indulgence written in the style of a “crusade indulgence” for the fight against heretics was proclaimed,⁴⁴ which became even more explosive given the raging Schmalkaldic War.

As a result of the excommunication of the archbishop, the previous coadjutor Adolf von Schauenburg was appointed as administrator of the archbishopric. This had happened even before the excommunication was published, at the beginning of July 1546.⁴⁵ However, as in the case of the ban, the execution of this decision was to take some time.

⁴⁴Paul III., *Das Päpstlich vrteil*, fol. IV Br-Bv .

⁴⁵ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*. 200.

The imperial letter to the estates

Encouraged by the excommunication and the papal action, Emperor Charles V also became active again in the Causa von Wied in December 1546. In a mandate, he addressed the estates of the Electorate of Cologne in order to finally achieve the deposition of the archbishop after the ban and excommunication had been imposed. Issued on December 21, the publication was printed in Cologne on January 3.⁴⁶

Jaspar von Gennep

The imperial mandate was printed by Jaspar von Gennep.⁴⁷ From 1544, during the entire conflict over the Reformation attempt, he was the house and court printer of the Catholic party, especially of the majority chapter in the city of Cologne, which had turned away from Hermann von Wied, as well as of the university. Through him, the Catholic side had the opportunity to print outside the archbishop's reach by distributing anti-Protestant writings along with letters from the pope and emperor in the city of Cologne, and thus, to enter into a competition via leaflets and propagandistic publications with the archbishop.⁴⁸ This, together with the Protestant counterparts printing in Bonn,⁴⁹ led to a veritable propaganda war for public opinion in the archbishopric and its subordinate dioceses. This can be seen in the immense number of over 250 prints published between 1540 and 1553, the death of Hermann von Wied, in the context of the Reformation attempt, which can be found in Schlüter's work.

⁴⁶ Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 329.

⁴⁷ Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 45.

⁴⁸ Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 3-5.

⁴⁹ The main printer for the reformation side, which fled from the city including the archbishop and the minority cathedral chapter, was Laurenz von der Mühlen. Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 3-4.

The frontispiece

In a pamphlet of this kind, the frontispiece can be considered a *regestum* or abstract. It summarises the main text along with the imperial decision. The text is followed by an imperial coat of arms.⁵⁰ This consists of a double-headed eagle, crowned with the imperial crown, with a breast shield *party per pale*. On the right-hand side, it is defined by a *Fesse*, on the left-hand side, by a *bendy*. Due to the monochrome print, the tinctures are missing, but it can be assumed that the shield on the right is the Austrian shield, *gules a fess argent*, and on the left the coat of arms of Burgundy, i.e. *bendy or and azure*. In this case, however, the depiction of the Burgundian coat of arms would be inaccurate, as it should consist of *Bendy of six or and azure, a bordure gules*. Nevertheless, contemporaries of this pamphlet probably recognised it as the coat of arms of the empire and the emperor. This coat of arms makes it clear that Charles V appears in the following pages as Emperor of the Holy Roman Empire, ruled by the House of Habsburg, which is connected with Burgundy. A complete coat of arms of Charles V, on the other hand, would also have included the arms of the Spanish crown, possibly evoking ideas of Spanish servitude, which was perceived as a contrast to *Teutscher Libertät*.⁵¹

The text on the frontispiece already summarises the content of the imperial mandate, and thus, informs the reader about the most important information of this publication. Since this was an imperial mandate, it was sent to the estates of the Archbishopric of Cologne. These estates are

⁵⁰ Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.1r.

⁵¹ *Spanischen Servitut* was for the contemporaries the tyrannical rule of Charles V and his successors in the colonies. It was strongly connected with the *leyenda negra* which developed with the appearance of the reports of Bartolomeo de las Casas. Schmidt, Peer. Schwarze Legende, Schmidt, Peer, “Schwarze Legende”, in: *Enzyklopädie der Neuzeit Online*. Consulted online on 14 December 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2352-0248_edn_COM_347405>. First published online: 2019.

In contrast to this, the concept of *Teutscher Libertät* can be seen as the self-image of the imperial princes. Schmidt, Georg, Freiheit, Schmidt, Georg, “Freiheit”, in: *Enzyklopädie der Neuzeit Online*. Consulted online on 14 December 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2352-0248_edn_COM_266320>. First published online: 2019.

mentioned one by one in order to address each of these groups directly - Counts, Lords, Knights, Nobility, Estates and Cities. They are summoned by the “kaiserlicher Macht” (imperial power) to appear before the cathedral chapter, the first institution in the territory, and before the imperial commissars on January 24, 1547, in the Domkapitel Haus in Cologne and to act in accordance with the following mandate.⁵² Thus, it was not only already obvious that a Landtag (diet for the territory of the archbishopric Cologne) was convened by the Emperor, for which the time and place had already been determined, but also that it would take place under the supervision of imperial commissars. This frontispiece shows astonishingly clearly that Archbishop von Wied, who had been excommunicated but still held on as sovereign, was not regarded as the head of the archbishopric. This role was rather assigned to the cathedral chapter, in this case, the part of the divided cathedral chapter recognised by the emperor. This elevation of the chapter indicates an attempt on the part of the emperor to bypass the level of his direct subordinate, the archbishop, as a prince of the empire, in order to find partners for handling the situation in Cologne at the level of the estates instead.

The aforementioned estates were not only the addressees of the imperial mandate but also the presumed recipients of this and other printed copies. Schlüter mentions in particular the Catholics or those in opposition to Hermann von Wied as the recipients of the prints commissioned by the cathedral chapter and von Gennepe.⁵³ In the case of this invitation to the Diet, which meant nothing other than the final deposition of the archbishop, it can also be assumed that it was sent to the reform-minded estates and published for the wider population in the city of Cologne and the towns of the archbishopric as well.

⁵² Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.1r.

⁵³ Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 3.

The date and attestation of the mandate

The location and dating of the imperial mandate were given in a dateline at the end of the text of the original document. “Given in our’s and the empires city Hall in Swabia the one and twentieth day of the month December Anno 7c. In the six and fortieth of our emperorship in the seven and twentieth and our realms one and thirtieth.”⁵⁴ It was thus given in the imperial city of Schwäbisch Hall by Emperor Charles V on December 21 1546. In addition to the date adjusted to the birth of Christ, a date according to the start of Charles' reign is also used. Here, both his twenty-seven years of reign as Emperor of the Holy Roman Empire of the German Nation and his thirty-one years of rule in “his realms” are mentioned in the text of the original document. This was presumably counted from his coming of age and the start of his reign over the Duchy of Burgundy. In the date according to the incarnation, the full spelling of the formula “*Anno Domini*” and “*Anno Incarnatione*” as well as the century after Christ's birth is dispensed with and simply represented by an abbreviated et cetera. The readers were aware of what had to be inserted for this ‘*et cetera*’, since these formulas were probably known to the intended readers of such documents. The text is signed with “*Carolus*” for Charles V. In print, this was of course not an authentic signature. For these reasons, and in order to ensure the authenticity of the contents of the text, various authentication features were also included in this print. Directly below the “signature” of Charles V, one can find “*Vidit Naves*”, a confirmation that the original document was seen and authenticated by Imperial Vice-Chancellor Johann Naves(1500-1547). As Imperial Vice-Chancellor, he was the head of the Chancellery of the Holy Roman Empire and the highest authority in charge of issuing documents. In the matter of Hermann von Wied's attempt at reformation, however, Naves also appeared as a diplomat, and

⁵⁴ “Geben in unser und des Reichs Stat Hall in Schwaben am eyn und zwentzigsten Tag des Monats Decembris Anno 7c. Im Sechs und viertzigsten unsers Kaiserthumbes im sieben und zwentzigsten und unserer Reiche im eyn und dreissigsten.”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.3r.

in 1545 and 1546, tried to intervene on behalf of the imperial Catholic side in order to prevent Hermann, and thus Kurköln, from turning to the Schmalkaldic League.⁵⁵

The notarial certifications

In a copy of the Erzbischöfliche Akademische Bibliothek Paderborn⁵⁶, handwritten authentications by two Cologne notaries follow the print of the imperial mandate. In contrast to the rest of the Early High German text, these authentications were written in Latin. Leonard von Fossa and Jakob von Dulcken confirmed the authenticity of the document on 3 January 1547. Leonard von Fossa was the secretary of the Cologne Cathedral Chapter or, as he wrote, “Public notary and secretary of the metropolitan church of Cologne.”⁵⁷ Jakob von Dulcken described himself as a cleric of the Cologne diocese, public scribe and notary for the matter of the archbishopric of Cologne by the imperial authority.⁵⁸

These handwritten notarial authentications could be particularly necessary for those copies that went from Cologne to the estates of the archbishopric, which tended to side with von Wied and the Reformation. A notarial certification was supposed to guarantee the authenticity of the content and pre-empt the fear of possible changes by the Catholic majority chapter or the pro-Catholic printer von Gennep. This seems especially expedient given the controversial nature of

⁵⁵ Aulinger, Rosemarie, “Naves, Johann von” in: *Neue Deutsche Biographie* 19 (1999), S. 1-2 [Online-Version]; URL: <https://www.deutsche-biographie.de/pnd137999100.html#ndbcontent>.

⁵⁶ As a digitised version found as EAB Paderborn VD16 ZV 4427, it is probably identical with the EAB Paderborn Th 1440a n.27 that Schlüter named. Schlüter, *Flug- und Streitschriften*, 329.

⁵⁷ “Notarius publicus, ac Metropolitana ecclesiae Colonien. Secretarius”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.3v.

⁵⁸ “Clericus Colonien. Dioecesis, publicus sacra Imperiali autoritate, et in venerabili curia Archiepiscopali Colonien. Causarum Notarius et Scriba”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol. 4r.

the imperial mandate since it contained nothing less than a call for the deposition of the sovereign by the estates.

The text of the imperial mandate

Following the protocol of imperial mandates, which had already developed in the High Middle Ages, the text of the printed document began with the Intitulatio and Salutatio. Emperor Charles V calls himself “by the grace of God Roman Emperor, semper Augustus, in Germania, Hispania, both Sicily, Jerusalem, Hungary, Dalmatia, Croatia, etc. King, Archduke of Austria, Duke of Burgundy, etc., Count of Flanders and Tyrol, etc.”⁵⁹ He addressed the “noble and honourable nobles loyal to us and the empire, all counts, lords, knights, nobles and towns of the archdiocese of Cologne”⁶⁰, to whom he offered his grace and wished all the best. Even in this highly formalised section of the mandate, it is clear that Charles V was concerned to address the estates of the Archbishopric of Cologne as subjects of the Empire and not those of the archbishop. On the one hand, they were to be flattered by being called noble, honourable and loyal;. On the other hand, the reference to loyalty is also a reminder of their duty to the empire and loyalty to the emperor and the Catholic cause, and not to the archbishop as sovereign.

⁵⁹ “von gottes gnaden Römischer Kayser, zu allen Zeiten mehrer des Reichs, in germanien, zu Hispanien, beyder Sicilien, Jerusalem, Hungeren, Dalmatien, Croatien, etc. Künig, Erzherzog zu Österreich, Herzug zu Burgundi etc., Graue zu Flandern und Tirol etc” The big Titulation is although only down to the level of counties. In the individual ranks, it was not used as a complete enumeration of all claimed territories - only the most important ones were mentioned while the rest was shortened with an “et cetera”’s in the Americas. It looks like this again is a try to focus solely on Charles V acting as emperor and the whole conflict only being an internal issue in the empire. All possible connections to the rule in the colonies as well as the leyenda negra should be averted as much as possible. See Footnote 50.

⁶⁰ “edelen ersamen unseren und des Reichs getrewen Nobiles, allen Graven, herrn, ritterschafft, adel stenden, und stätten des Erzstiftes cöln”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

The following *narratio* describes the situation in the Archbishopric of Cologne, which was perceived as maladministration and led to the issue of the imperial mandate. Charles V reported that these events were brought to his attention, so he did not act from a purely external point of view. “us reached believably”⁶¹ Here he referred not only to simple reports that had reached him but also to the appeals of the Catholic estates from the past years and the trial against the archbishop that had been going on since 1444. As the origin of the complaints, reference is made to the “newly established preachers”.⁶² These new preachers were Martin Butzer as well as those Protestant preachers who had contributed to the spread of the Einfältiges Bedenkens after its publication.⁶³ Martin Butzer's sermons from 1542 onwards revealed that Hermann von Wied's plans for reforming the church constitution had not been within the framework of the Catholic Church and of the changes demanded by the emperor at the Regensburg Diet, but would also take up reformatory ideas. Since Butzer's sermons, however, the situation had only worsened. This mandate aimed to ensure that Cologne did not fall into “apostasy and ruin”⁶⁴ for lack of “understanding”⁶⁵ on the part of the Reformation-minded estates. The “lack of a proper head”⁶⁶ was made responsible for this possible decline. The blame was thus placed directly on Hermann von Wied, even though he was not even mentioned by name in the entire text since he was not qualified to preside over his territory as sovereign. The urgency of installing his successor Adolf von Schauenburg, who was never mentioned by name either, also alluded to the fact that the Electorate of Cologne had been in practice without a recognised sovereign due to Hermann von Wied's ban and excommunication. This could probably only be expressed this clearly since the excommunication had been imposed on him a few months

⁶¹ “*uns gelangt gläublich an*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

⁶² “*Newen aufgestellten Predicandten*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

⁶³ Badaea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 78.

⁶⁴ “*abfall und verderben*”

⁶⁵ “*Einsehens*”

⁶⁶ “*mangel eines ordentlichen Haupts*”

earlier. The Emperor wanted to lead the Archdiocese of Cologne with its estates and subjects back to “grace and the good”.⁶⁷ In addition to this return to the grace of the Catholic Church and the empire, the dignity, status and nature of the archbishopric should be preserved, and harm and disadvantage should be averted from the subjects who were dependent on the sovereign. The status quo ante was presented as the ideal perspective, in other words, “the good old days” before the Reformation. However, this projection was not entirely honest, since the need for reform had been recognised and negotiated in Regensburg. The Regensburg Interim may have not applied directly to the Archbishopric of Cologne, but the need for reforms was just as prevalent there. Appeals were also made to the dignity of the archbishopric as an entity; it was hardly just a question of the loss of an albeit important Catholic metropolitan see, but for Charles as a Habsburg, the majority of the electorates for the Catholic side and the election of a successor from his dynasty were in danger. In Saxony and Brandenburg, two electors were already Protestant, the Electoral Palatinate still belonged to the group of the indecisive, and the Catholic majority consisted only of Habsburg-controlled Bohemia and the three ecclesiastical electors. A possible turn away of Cologne from Catholicism was connected with a threatening institutional crisis for the empire or at least with the threatening loss of the imperial throne for the House of Habsburg. This became particularly clear when the Emperor spoke of the Archdiocese of Cologne as “our and the Empire's most noble member”.⁶⁸

As a positive counterpart to the imperial action, the action of the estates “among themselves”⁶⁹ was now mentioned. They were given the actual role of governing the territory, since the head, the sovereign, cannot be relied upon, or at the time of the mandate, there was no legitimate

⁶⁷ “*gnaden und gutem*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

⁶⁸ “*unseres und des Reichs vornehmsten Glieder*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

⁶⁹ “*unter sich selbst*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

office bearer. The Emperor's intensified intervention is justified by his and the estates' unsuccessful attempts to solve the problems of church reform and the defiance of Hermann von Wied. Here, too, the mandate remains relatively vague as to what has been done and what has failed, and it does not go into any further detail about the situation that is perceived as a problem; the aim is once again to avert further evil, or more precisely “bad advise and disadvantage”, from the archbishopric but also from the subjects. The emperor had decided to finally act with the “inspiration of the Almighty”.⁷⁰ This divine inspiration was probably less a vision of Charles than of the papal excommunication in the early summer of 1546. In the following part, the emperor alternates between flattering words towards the estates and implicit threats. He emphasises that his action would only promise success, “could be done most conducive” if it were done with the knowledge and assistance of the Estates.⁷¹ The Emperor wanted to refrain from a deposition from above, but instead, carry it out consensually with the involvement of the Estates of Cologne. Not only should action by the emperor alone be impossible, but even the decision of the *Disputatio* has disguised him as the decision-maker. The summoning of the estates was done by the cathedral chapter and the “*Afterdechant*” (Subdeacon), which he describes as “honourable and our dear ones”.⁷² Even though Charles names them as the inviting ones, the summoning to the Diet was done by him. This is the actual legal content of the mandate. The estates are summoned to meet in Cologne on January 24 1547 in the house of the cathedral chapter to discuss the case of Hermann von Wied and to reach a decision on the solution of the problems under the supervision of the cathedral chapter, that is to say, the Catholic majority chapter, and imperial commissioners. Even in this most concrete part of the mandate, Hermann's deposition is not mentioned, but only implicitly alluded to. Instead, peace

⁷⁰ “*unrath unnd nachtheils*”; “*verlehung des Allmächtigisten*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

⁷¹ “*am füeglichsten geschehen könnte*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

⁷² “*ehrsam und unsere lieben*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

and unity among the estates and subjects (*Landfrieden*) were to be maintained and the “prevention of further disputes and bad advise” was to be achieved.⁷³

The presence of all the estates at the Diet is to be ensured in a particularly forceful manner. Thus, they are not only requested and required by the Emperor, but he also seriously commands them to appear with this letter. That this is not just a request from the Emperor, but rather an order, is clear from the fact that this call is made “especially by roman imperial power” and is linked to a reminder of the duties towards the emperor, the empire and the archbishopric.⁷⁴ Excuses and refusals would not be tolerated, but anyone who is genuinely prevented from attending would be given the opportunity to send an envoy with extensive decision-making authority.⁷⁵ The repeatedly mentioned unity of the estates is to be achieved through complete or at least extensive presence at the Diet, in order to lend a broader legitimation to the deposition of the archbishop and the appointment of his successor. The deposition should not only be carried out by the remaining Catholic majority chapter, but by the Diet itself.

That this Diet and the question of the deposition weren't an open-ended question becomes clear in the following paragraph. Imperial commissars will also be present, who are to report on the emperor's behalf which measures are most suitable to ensure peace and pacification. The estates were asked to listen to these proposals and to decide “to do and act, execute and help to carry out that” as the urgency of the situation required.⁷⁶ “That” in this case referred to the emperor's plans, that is to say the deposition of Hermann von Wied and the appointment of the coadjutor

⁷³ “*verhütung vorstehender weiterung und unrath*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

⁷⁴ “*insbesonds von Römisch kayserlicher macht*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

⁷⁵ Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.2r.

⁷⁶ “*das jenig zu tun und zu handeln, vollstrecken und zu vollziehen helfen*”; Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol.3r.

von Schauenburg as his successor. A different decision would be neither expected nor tolerated. This is also evident in the last sentence of the text before the date. Instead of formulating a concrete legal consequence for the violation of this imperial mandate in the sense of a *sanctio*, another appeal is made to the estates. A violation, a non-attendance, but obviously also a non-unanimous Diet resolution not agreeable to the emperor should be avoided in order to prevent a continuation of the grievances and to avert harm to the archbishopric, its estates and subjects.⁷⁷

The threat of the imperial army under Maximilian von Büren, which was on its way to Cologne and was at the gates of Cologne at the time of the Diet, hangs over the whole scene.⁷⁸ Acting against this mandate would cause negative consequences - for instance, military intervention in Electoral Cologne by imperial troops, and thus, far greater material ramifications than the battle by leaflets and other prints; or the excommunication and ostracism of the sovereign. The seriousness of such a danger was also known to the population and the estates, through the indulgence against heretics granted by the pope and through the letter of Johann Baptista Cicada from the previous year. After this letter, it was clear to everyone that the emperor had given the estates two options - to depose Hermann von Wied and recognise Adolf von Schauenburg, which would mean a return to the bosom of the Church and the empire; or to continue the conflict and side with Hermann, which would have resulted in military intervention by the emperor. In the end, Charles V decided to depose Hermann himself, but the emperor kept up the semblance of an orderly process and deposition from “below” - although a deposition from “above” had already taken place through the ban and excommunication.

⁷⁷ Karl V., *Römischer Keyserlicher Maiestat*, fol. 3r.

⁷⁸ Schlüter, *Flug-und Streitschriften*, 215.

Consequences of the imperial mandate

Hermann von Wied, who in the course of 1546 had sent notes of protest against his imperial ban and excommunication, and had also tried to circumvent a demand for his abdication, planned to make a last attempt to remain in power at this Diet.⁷⁹ He wanted to appear before the estates in Cologne in person, and thus, to prevent his final deposition. Nonetheless, this endeavour failed as the imperial commissars already reached Cologne on 22 January 1547.⁸⁰ As already indicated in the imperial letter, the presence of the imperial troops outside the city and the presence of the commissars at the Diet were necessary to prevent the secular estates from once again avoiding a final decision on the deposition of the archbishop. In the end, however, they decided to depose Hermann von Wied and install Adolf von Schauenburg as administrator. Historians disagree on the question of whether Hermann subsequently abdicated on 24 or 25 January or February. Badea explains conclusively why this could not have happened, but this theory is still found in older scholarship - for example, Stephan Laux has phrased it as “*Resignation*” (resignation), Dorothee Mußnug, as “*Verzicht auf seine Ämter*” (Renunciation of his offices) and Kloosterhuis, as “*Abdankung*” (Abdication).⁸¹ The candidacy of Adolf von Schauenburg represented the ideal compromise for the succession. He had family connections to the Wetterau counts, was probably a good Catholic, despite rumours of his sympathies for Protestantism, and had already been active as coadjutor at the centre of the archbishopric's power since 1533.⁸² After his deposition, Hermann von Wied remained in the

⁷⁹ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 202-215.

⁸⁰ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 216.

⁸¹ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 217; Laux, *Reformationsversuche in Kurköln*, 74; Mußnug, *Acht und Bann*, 265; Kloosterhuis, *Erasmusjünger*, 75.

⁸² Hatzfeld “Die Wetterauer Grafen”, 228.

territory of Kurköln and retired to his hunting lodge at Buschhoven before returning to Wied Castle, where he died in 1522.⁸³

Conclusion

So can Hermann von Wied's deposition be described as a revolution? In addition, is the imperial mandate to be understood as a call for revolution? Of the characteristics of a revolution as defined by Niggemann, Reichardt and Pincus, hardly any can be found in the Cologne Reformation. Hermann von Wied was deposed and the Protestant part of the Cologne elite lost its influence and power. Nonetheless, his successor Adolf von Schauenburg came from the same circles and the Catholic ruling class of the Archbishopric Cologne consolidated their position, even though it had been weekend during the Attempt at Reformation. What is given, however, is an ideological, and in this case religious, reorientation. Economic structures did not play a considerable role in the entire conflict. A violent upheaval did not take place either, certainly not carried out by a movement from below. However, had the decision of the estates in January 1547 been different, this could even have led to a possible conflict with the emperor and further disruption of the Landfrieden, which then would have had to be referred to as a revolution. The possibility of unrest during the diet seemed at least likely enough for the imperial troops to be ordered to intervene in an emergency.⁸⁴ Thus, Hermann von Wied's deposition could, to a certain extent, be described as a prevention of a revolution. From the point of view of a revolution, the Cologne Reformation attempt and its end appear to fit perfectly into the framework. For example, Pincus' thesis of revolution as a decision of direction within a process of modernisation, can be found. The church constitution had to be reformed but the question that arose was whether it should be an internal Catholic reform, an Erasmian-

⁸³ Laux, *Reformationsversuche in Kurköln*, 74.

⁸⁴ Badea, *Kurfürstliche Präeminenz*, 215.

inspired one, or oriented towards one of the Protestant denominations. This did not lead to a revolution, but no less significantly, to the deposition of an elector, through a complex interplay between the estates, the church and the emperor.

Although it is not a call for revolution, Charles V's Imperial Mandate, in which he addresses the Cologne estates, shows the complexity of deposing a prince in the sixteenth century. Since violence and a breach of the Landfrieden were to be prevented, an interplay between the emperor, the pope and the estates was necessary to depose Hermann von Wied as archbishop of Cologne. Institutionalised trials were followed by an imperial ban by the emperor and excommunication by the pope. Since even these depositions from "above" did not ultimately lead to an end to the rule, Charles V felt compelled to exert pressure on the estates to avoid a forcible deposition by military means, so that they decided to depose the archbishop from "below" at the Landtag in 1547, thus putting an end to the Cologne Reformation attempt.

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